

Unraveling the microbiological world: practical experiences in public high schools in Brazil

Desvendando o mundo microbiológico: experiências práticas em escolas públicas de ensino médio no Brasil

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ABSTRACT

Microbiology plays a fundamental role in studying the importance of microorganisms in the human body, environment, food and in other aspects covered by this science. Finding a connection between microbiology and everyday life is not an easy task. This study aimed to insert two microbiology practices (inoculation of microorganisms from common objects and Gram staining) for High School students from two Brazilian public schools and to evaluate the importance of these practices in the development of these students' scientific knowledge. In total, approximately 65 students from High School classes were included in the actions developed by this study. After the practices and application of the surveys, it was possible to obtain interesting data about the students' perception as 85% of the students said they were very interested in the practice's contents. The practical activities provided students with the opportunity to observe and study microorganisms in a controlled environment and have the potential to awaken the student's interest in learning this subject.

Keywords: bacteria, education, fungi, educational practices, science communication.

RESUMO

A microbiologia tem papel fundamental no estudo da importância dos microrganismos no corpo humano, no meio ambiente, nos alimentos e em outros aspectos abrangidos por esta ciência. Encontrar uma conexão entre a microbiologia e a vida cotidiana não é uma tarefa fácil. Este estudo teve como objetivo inserir duas práticas de microbiologia (Inoculação de microrganismos de objetos de importância comum e coloração de Gram) para alunos do ensino

médio de duas escolas públicas brasileiras e avaliar o impacto dessas práticas no desenvolvimento do conhecimento científico desses alunos. No total, cerca de 65 alunos de turmas do ensino médio foram contemplados nas ações desenvolvidas por este estudo. Após as práticas e aplicação dos questionários, foi possível obter dados interessantes sobre a percepção dos alunos, pois 85% dos alunos afirmaram estar muito interessados nos conteúdos das práticas. As atividades práticas proporcionaram aos alunos a oportunidade de observar e estudar microrganismos em ambiente controlado e têm o potencial de despertar o interesse do aluno em aprender este assunto.

Palavras-chave: bactérias, educação, fungos, práticas educativas, divulgação científica.

1 INTRODUCTION

Microbiology is a scientific field dedicated to the study of microscopic organisms (which are mainly unicellular beings, invisible to the naked eye) and their importance for life on the planet. However, for most people, the elements of this science and its influence go unnoticed, since many are unaware of the interactions that microorganisms establish with the environment. Generally, their existence is only recognized to bring to light the diseases caused by them (FELIX et al., 2020).

Microbiology plays a fundamental role in studying the importance of microorganisms in the human body, in the environment, in food and in other aspects. In this sense, it is evident that the misconceptions about microorganisms that are widespread in society must be clarified, in order to enable the presentation of a comprehensive knowledge about them and highlight their benefits for ecology, the common good and individual well-being. Thus, it is crucial not to limit microbiology to its negative aspects only, but also to emphasize its positive contributions (TORTORA et al., 2017).

The presentation to students of the different environments in which microorganisms are present, also emphasizing their benefits, is considered relevant by some researchers. However, due to the nature of these organisms, which are invisible to the naked eye, students may face difficulties in internalizing the concepts. Therefore, it is up to the teacher to seek strategies that facilitate the understanding of the theme and improve student learning (FERREIRA, 2010).

Finding a connection between microbiology and everyday life is an easy task, but it is necessary to seek methodologies that stimulate and instigate students in the search for knowledge, promoting correlation and applicability of this science in everyday life. By establishing this connection, students can understand how microorganisms are present in different aspects of everyday life, such as food, health, industry and the environment. This provides greater relevance and meaning to the study of microbiology, capturing students' interest and encouraging their scientific curiosity (TIMMIS et al., 2019).

Researchers in the educational area point out that the formation of critical students requires a reformulation of teaching methods, considering the prior knowledge of each individual, as well as the social, political and cultural aspects involved. After an in-depth analysis, new approaches to student training are proposed, aiming to contribute to the achievement of the learning process and to the development of a democratic society. This approach considers the individuality of students, promoting a more contextualized, inclusive education that values the diversity of experiences and perspectives. By recognizing and integrating these elements, it is possible to provide a more meaningful education that encourages critical thinking, reflection and active participation of students in the learning process (DE OLIVEIRA et al., 2019; ROCHA & PINTO, 2020).

The use of Petri dishes with colonies of microorganisms is of significant importance in the learning of microbiology by public school students. This practice provides students with the opportunity to observe and study microorganisms in a controlled environment. By visualizing colonies growing in Petri dishes, students can experience microbial diversity in a concrete way and understand the importance of microorganisms in various aspects, such as health, ecology and industry. In addition, handling Petri dishes and carrying out inoculation techniques promote the development of practical skills, such as asepsis and aseptic techniques, fundamental in the field of microbiology (ONO et al., 2020).

Given this, this study aimed to insert two microbiology practices for high school students from two Brazilian public schools and to evaluate the importance of these practices in the development of these students' scientific knowledge.

1.1 MICROORGANISMS

Microorganisms are responsible for most of the planet's biomass, despite their small size (SOONG et al., 2020). In aquatic environments, microorganisms form the basis of the food chain and provide much of the oxygen necessary for the respiration of macroscopic organisms. In soils, they play a major role in the decomposition of organic matter and in the recycling of elements, participating in biogeochemical cycles (TORTORA et al., 2017).

Most microorganisms pose no risk to humans and actually play a crucial role in the production of foods such as dairy, bread, and beverages through chemical reactions that occur during the fermentation process. However, it is essential to acquire practical knowledge about microorganisms in the field of microbiology (TING et al., 2021). Microorganisms can be present in any environment and, on some occasions, can cause damage, such as food deterioration, diseases and environmental contamination. Therefore, having knowledge about these microorganisms allows taking measures against the pathologies they cause, controlling their transmission and applying treatments to the diseases (TUMOLO et al., 2020).

There are several forms of life that are classified as microorganisms, exhibiting a wide diversity of structures. These organisms may consist of simple cells or may have more complex structures. In addition, there are microorganisms considered special, as they are not composed of cells and have peculiar characteristics. Among commonly studied microorganisms we can highlight bacteria, which are unicellular with a relatively simple structure (TORTORA et al., 2017). They can be autotrophs or heterotrophs. These organisms are classified as prokaryotes as they do not have a nucleus surrounded by a membrane in their cells. Prokaryotic organisms are present in virtually all habitats on the planet and are believed to have been the first living beings to exist on Earth, due to their simple structure and their presence in environments considered extreme. The Archaea, found in these environments, lack peptidoglycan cell walls and, so far, are not known to cause disease in humans (DECKER et al., 2022).

Unlike bacteria, fungi are living organisms that have a defined nucleus, being classified as eukaryotes. These organisms can be unicellular or multicellular and are exclusively heterotrophic. True fungi have a cell wall composed of chitin, a polysaccharide also found in the exoskeleton of arthropods, which indicates a closer relationship with animals than with plants. Fungi of direct interest in microbiology are those that do not produce fruiting bodies (GHINI & KIMATI, 2019).

There are single-celled fungi, such as yeasts, which play an important role in food production. They are the main components of biological yeast, an ingredient used in bread making. In addition, there are multicellular fungi, such as molds, which are often found in moldy breads and fruits. What is visible in moldy foods is the mycelium, which is the set of hyphae, filaments that make up the body of the fungus. Occasionally they can cause disease in plants and animals. In people, the most common fungal infections are mycoses and chilblains (FREIMOSER et al., 2019).

Viruses, meanwhile, are acellular organisms, obligate intracellular parasites that depend on host cells to replicate. They basically consist of genetic material protected by a protein coat called a capsid. Viruses can contain single-stranded or double-stranded DNA or RNA as their genetic material. When they infect bacteria, they are called bacteriophages. There are many diseases caused by these organisms, transmitted in various ways, such as flu, mumps, hepatitis, dengue and some sexually transmitted diseases such as herpes and acquired immunodeficiency syndrome (AIDS) (WANG et al., 2021).

Studying microbiology and understanding the diverse microbial groups gives students a deeper insight into the importance of microorganisms in our everyday lives, health, industry and environment. This promotes a solid base of scientific knowledge and stimulates scientific curiosity about the microscopic world around us.

1.2 THE TEACHING OF MICROBIOLOGY AND ITS IMPORTANCE

Nowadays, it is common to see in schools a reality in which students have deficiencies in the learning process, often related to the construction of mistaken knowledge. This situation can be attributed, in large part, to the use of ineffective teaching methodologies. Krasilchik (2008) reports in his study:

Although the importance of practical classes is widely recognized, in reality they make up a very small portion of biology courses because, according to teachers, there is not enough time to organize the material, they lack confidence to control the class, knowledge to organize experiments and also lack adequate equipment and facilities (KRASILCHIK, 2008, p. 87).

Complementing this idea, it can be said that, in most schools, Science and Biology classes are taught in a merely traditional way. Using this kind of teaching methodology, it is not possible to implement efficient and meaningful scientific learning.

According to Pinto et al. (2021), basic knowledge about microbiology is extremely important for building more aware citizens able to face everyday life. This is because this area of knowledge is directly linked to health and personal hygiene, as well as other important aspects related to the functioning of the environment. In this way, this theme deserves special attention in the Teaching of Science and Biology. However, Cassanti et al. (2008) state that, despite its great relevance, microbiology is largely neglected by teachers, being treated in a merely traditional way within the content referring to living beings, content normally addressed in the 7th year of Elementary School and in the 2nd year from High School.

De Freitas Zompero (2009) states in her study:

It is essential that previous conceptions about microorganisms and their correlations with human health and the environment are identified. This identification helps the Science teacher, as well as the Biology teacher, in the elaboration of activities that promote the association with everyday microbiology and legitimize the improvement and consolidation of the students' citizenship (Zompero, 2009, p. 32).

Without the existence of efficient teaching-learning strategies, the world of microorganisms becomes extremely abstract for Basic Education students, as it is not easily observed directly by the senses. Admittedly, this apparent flaw in the correlation between microbiology and everyday life makes it difficult to learn about this topic, which proves to be of paramount importance for well-being and quality of life.

It is extremely necessary to develop activities that provide effective teaching of microbiology, seeking to meet the needs of students. Considering the reality in most Brazilian public schools, where the lack of resources is reflected in the current situation, it is also necessary to adopt simple and low-cost techniques.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 STUDY AREA

The study was carried out in a school located in the city of Fortaleza (3° 43' 6" South; 38° 32' 36" West) and another in Maranguape (3° 53' 26" South, 38° 40' 55" West), both located in the State of Ceará, Brazil. The Fortaleza's school (School 1) has a diverse student community, with approximately 1,200 enrolled students. These students are guided by a team of around 70 teachers, who claim to provide an environment conducive to learning and personal growth (BRASIL, 2021). The Maranguape's school (School 2) has a student community comprising of approximately 900 students enrolled. These students are assisted by a team of approximately 49 teachers. The school's teachers say they are committed to offering a quality education, providing students with a stimulating environment (BRASIL, 2021).

2.2 PRACTICE 1: 'MICROORGANISMS ARE EVERYWHERE'

This practice aims to demonstrate that the microorganisms that surround us are propagated in the environment by collecting samples from different locations and later, by reading the results to prove the diversity and density of microorganisms in different environments. We used Petri dishes containing

nutrient agar medium, flexible and sterilized cotton swabs, incubation oven, sterile saline solution and 70% ethanol.

The sterile swabs were soaked in sterile saline solution and then passed through commonly used utensils such as pens, doors and cell phones (Figure 1). The rod was passed over the surface of the culture medium, by exhaustion. Then, the plate was identified, Nutrient Agar plates were incubated at 37°C for 3 days and the results were presented to the students (VERMELHO, 2006).

Figures 1a and 1b– Collection of biological material and subsequent inoculation in a plate with culture medium

Source: Authors, 2023.

2.3 PRACTICE 2 – OBSERVATION OF RESULTS AND GRAM STAINING

After incubation, the microbial populations formed on the surface of the medium, called colonies, were observed with the naked eye. The students evaluated the colonies by their characteristics, which we called morphocolonial (TORTORA et al., 2017).

Despite being chemically distinct from the environment that surrounds them, bacteria are almost colorless, not presenting enough contrast with the environment in which they are found, which makes their visualization difficult. The chemical difference between bacteria and the medium is what allows us to distinguish them through staining, as the dye does not react with the external medium, making them, when stained, more visible under the microscope. In this way we will be able to observe its fundamental forms, dimensions and

arrangements. Thus, the main objective of this practice was to stain a slide using the Gram method.

Students used bacteria previously identified in Practice 1. A glass slide was cleaned, and the side of the slide where the smear was taken was identified, as well as its origin. Standard protocol was then used for Gram staining (TORTORA et al., 2017).

Figures 2a and 2b – Preparation of slides and students executing Gram staining

Source: Authors, 2023

2.4 SURVEY AND DATA ANALYSES

To better understand the students' perception of the applied microbiology practices, a survey containing ten questions was applied to each student. Some of the questions were: “What was your reaction when performing the practice of collecting and inoculating materials on nutrient agar plates?”; “What kind of microorganisms did you observe in the Petri dishes?”; and “Do you believe that this practice helped to better understand the presence and importance of microorganisms in our daily lives?”.

Basic statistical tests were used for data processing. It started with a descriptive analysis of the data to obtain an overview of the replies. Statistical measures such as mean, median, mode, standard deviation, etc. were calculated. This helped to identify general patterns in the data and provide background information about the distribution of responses.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In total, approximately 65 students from high school classes were included in the actions developed by this study. Practical biology classes are extremely important for high school students, as they provide a concrete and tangible experience that complements theoretical learning (FELIX et al., 2020). Educational activities of this type allow students to develop essential skills such as observation, data collection, analysis and interpretation of results. By experiencing biological processes in practice, they are encouraged to think critically and make decisions based on evidence, fundamental skills for the contemporary world. In addition, practical classes stimulate students' interest in the discipline, awakening their curiosity and motivating them to explore the world of biology in a deeper way. By having the opportunity to manipulate materials and interact with living organisms, they are able to understand abstract concepts in a more concrete and meaningful way (CÁRIAS et al., 2019).

Silva (2014) gave practical and theoretical Biology classes to high school students and evaluated them after each methodology used, showing that after practical classes there was a significant increase in the number of correct answers in the learning assessments compared to theoretical classes. Practical classes show students how science is present in everyday situations, explaining natural phenomena, reactions that happen in our body and even social aspects. In addition, experimental activities are formed by attributes that arouse interest and curiosity in students, such as tactile, visual and sound characters.

Students attended by this study suggested that more practical activities in laboratory should be carried out in school, especially in those class contents in which experimental activities were not developed, even though they could be performed. Others reported their perception of the content taught based on their experience in the practical class. In some cases, the practical experiences developed in schools were transformative, directing these students' choice of profession.

“Being able to understand a little more about this world of microorganisms made me want to learn more and apply what I learned in my future work. Maybe I can work in healthcare.” (Student from School 2)

It is important that the teacher recognizes and identifies what the students already know about the subject, as it is through prior knowledge, correct or alternative, that the new construction becomes effective and permanent. All the practices elaborated in this study are associated with daily life and can be used as a “trigger” in the teaching-learning process, valuing prior knowledge.

As for the results of Practice 1, the microorganisms could be classified in colony size, aspect, pigmentation, surface and edges. As can be seen in Figure 3, there was a great diversity of microorganisms on the different surfaces from which they were collected, such as water bottles, water drinkers, bathtub drain, cellphones, rings and the floor of the classroom, all chosen by the students.

Fig 3 - Diversity of microorganisms inoculated by students.

Source: Authors, 2023

On objects such as cell phones, students observed circular, medium and large bacterial colonies, with a predominance of yellow and white, translucent and opaque colors. In places such as the refrigerator, there was a predominance of large fungal colonies, in some situations occupying the entire plate with nutrient agar medium. The students carried out a search on the internet and concluded

that fungi can be found in the refrigerator due to the favorable conditions that this environment provides for their growth. The refrigerator is a humid place, with low temperatures and available organic matter, especially in food not stored properly. These conditions are conducive to the development of fungi, which can spread rapidly in contaminated food, forming visible mycelium, as in mold. On the handrail, small and yellow bacterial colonies stood out for their quantity. The diversity of bacterial colonies suggests the presence of different bacterial species or strains on the school handrail, highlighting the importance of hygiene and maintaining clean environments to prevent the spread of pathogenic microorganisms.

“I found it very interesting to see the different types of organisms that grew in Petri dishes with culture medium. I was able to learn more about the subject than if I had only used the book.” (Student from School 1)

Despite being chemically distinct from the environment that surrounds them, bacteria are almost colorless, not presenting enough contrast with the environment in which they are found, which makes their visualization difficult. The chemical difference between bacteria and the medium is what makes them distinguishable through staining, as the dye does not react with the external medium, making them, when stained, stand out under the microscope. In this way, students could observe the bacteria's fundamental forms, dimensions and arrangements (TORTORA et al., 2017). As for the results of Gram staining, it was possible to observe different bacterial types and arrangements (Figures 4a and 4b). It is noteworthy that the preparation of slides and smears was carried out by the researcher and the students contributed with the staining and evaluation of the results obtained from the Microscope.

Figures 4a and 4b- Bacteria stained and viewed under a microscope at 1000x magnification

Source: Authors, 2023

When performing the Gram staining, students could observe that bacteria are divided into two main groups: Gram-positive, which were colored purple, and Gram-negative, pink. Gram-positive bacteria have a thick cell wall composed mainly of peptidoglycan, while Gram-negative bacteria have a more complex cell wall with an outer layer of lipopolysaccharide. From this observation, students were able to understand that the Gram staining not only helps to differentiate groups of bacteria, but also provides information about their structure and characteristics. Furthermore, they were able to learn that the Gram staining is an important step in the identification of bacteria and can be used as an initial tool for bacterial classification.

“I didn't know bacteria were naturally colorless, as I always saw them colored in books.” (Student from School 1)

After the practices and application of the surveys, it was possible to obtain interesting data about the students' perception after the execution of the research activities. 74% of the students said they were not interested in the content of the lesson before the start of the practices. After the microbiology practices, 85% of the students said they were very interested in the contents. This shows how hands-on activities in microbiology can provide students with a tangible and

engaging experience with the concepts and techniques studied in the classroom. Rather than just reading about the topics, they had the opportunity to actually conduct experiments, observe microscopic organisms, and directly interact with the study material. This hands-on experience aroused students' curiosity and increased their interest.

Of the evaluated students, 80% stated that they had no problems in carrying out the practical activities. This was due to the concern of the researchers involved in this study to send a clear message to the students. Thus, in order to accomplish this, the theory behind the experiments was explained before the practices, using clear language, and the students were closely monitored in all stages of the activities.

94% of the students stated that the practices helped to better understand the presence and importance of microorganisms in their daily lives. By investigating how microorganisms relate to the environment and to humans, students begin to understand the importance of microorganisms in fundamental processes such as the decomposition of organic matter, the recycling of nutrients, and the maintenance of ecological balance. They also learn about the participation of microorganisms in different areas, such as the production of fermented foods, the pharmaceutical industry and biotechnology.

4 FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

When learning lacks meaning, it loses its cognitive depth and becomes a mechanical process. Raw data, on its own, is merely a collection of facts, but when organized and contextualized, it transforms into information. However, information alone does not constitute to knowledge. Knowledge arises when information is connected to existing understanding. The responsibility for constructing knowledge lies with the individual, who can only achieve it through intentional effort. By engaging in active problem-solving, students develop a deeper understanding of the subject matter and enhance their critical thinking skills.

The expository class is unidirectional, which means that it is based on the passive student who receives the information transmitted by the teacher. It is characterized as a teaching method that reduces the chances of the student reaching a high cognitive level. Transmitting insufficient information in the teaching-learning process, as the accumulation of information, does not make the student assign meanings and consequently learn the content. Thus, problematization and practical activities have the potential to awaken the student's interest in learning how to learn, contributing to the formation of professional citizens who are critically positioned to improve the society in which they are inserted.

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